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What can heathers tell us about the origins of biological diversity?

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In *Heathers 8* (2011), Ted Oliver described a field trip during which we collected species of *Erica* in Madagascar. This expedition was a part of a continuing research project on *Erica* in which Dirk Bellstedt (also at the University of Stellenbosch) and I are working with Ted to ask one of the most fundamental questions in biology: that is “What are the origins of biological diversity?” or, put another way, “How do species (such as our own, *Homo sapiens*) come into existence?”

If we want to address this kind of question, we have to look back in time, deep into the evolutionary history of life. The box-office takings from *Jurassic Park* illustrate a human fascination with lost, ancient worlds (or at least some of the toothier aspects of them). Whilst that particular scenario may be a little far-fetched, real evolutionary biology is, in a way, still an attempt to reconstruct the ancient past. The discipline is not all retrospective, though. Evolution is a dynamic, ongoing process, and the relevance of the answers we can get extends from the past to our present and into the future. For example, we might learn about the impact on biodiversity of past phenomena, such as climate change and mass-extinction events, and use this knowledge to predict the future impact of similar, human-mediated, current events (of which we are all too aware).

I have come to exactly the right place to look for these answers, because if you want to study the origin of species you should go somewhere where it has been happening a lot. And here I am – right in the middle of the Cape Floristic Region (CFR; Figure 1), an area of unparalleled biological richness choc-a-bloc with plant species found nowhere else on earth.

The south-western corner of the African continent is blessed with a Mediterranean-type climate with warm, dry summers and mild, wet winters. It is not just ideal for producing wine and having braais (South Africa’s variant on the barbecue): the CFR is botanically remarkable. Its area is tiny, but in the 90,000 sq. km (an area smaller than Portugal but a little more than Ireland), there are around 9,000 species, 70% of which are endemic – without human intervention they do not grow anywhere else in the world. To put it in context, this kind of diversity is more what you would expect in the hyper-diverse wet tropics close to the Equator; whilst the endemism is comparable to that of isolated oceanic islands (Linder 2003).

To evolutionary biologists, the CFR is like a giant natural laboratory. To better understand what drives the process of speciation in general, we can ask “What is it that has made the CFR so species-rich?” and set about testing plausible hypotheses. This we can do using the vast source of data represented by the

Figure 1. The Cape Floristic Region (CFR). The red dots correspond to Vanrhynsdorp in the North-West, Port Elizabeth in the East, and Cape Town and Stellenbosch in the South-West. A = Cape Peninsula; B = Hottentots-Holland; C = Kogelberg (South-West region); D= Cedarberg; E = Ceres; F= Hex River Mountains (North-West region). Satellite images are from Google Earth. Data SIO, NOAA, US Navy, NGA, GEBCO; Image © 2011 TerraMetrics; Image IBACO © 2011 Cnes/Spot Image.

CFR's numerous species. And, if the CFR is our lab, then our fattest "lab rats" are the disproportionately big Cape plant groups: the so-called "Cape Clades", just 33 of which together represent around half of the species richness of the CFR (Linder 2003). In the CFR, the iris family is very diverse (just two subfamilies, Ixioidae and Nivenioideae, include 516 species), as is the Restionaceae (the Cape reeds; 340 species) and, of course, the Proteaceae (264 species) including the archetypal *Protea*. By a long way the largest of the lot, and therefore offering the biggest single source of data, is the genus *Erica*. The most up-to-date figure for species numbers in the CFR is 692.

The process of speciation can basically be summarized as the divergence of one interbreeding group of individuals to become two or more reproductively exclusive new groups. How might this occur? One possibility is that the groups became physically isolated – by chance dispersal of an individual to somewhere remote, or by the appearance of a new barrier – a mountain chain, or a desert or rising ocean caused by climate change, for example. The groups may "drift" genetically over time and eventually become sufficiently different that they are no longer reproductively compatible, even if they do subsequently meet again

Figure 2. Two potential modes of speciation: **a** by the splitting-up of a geographically widespread species into two daughter species with more restricted distributions; **b** by specialization of one daughter species to a different pollinator.

(Figure 2a). Another possibility is that the way in which plants reproduce might change – a change for example in the way a flower is structured might attract a different pollinating insect, effectively isolating groups that might live amongst each other, simply because of the restricted way the pollen travels (Figure 2b).

Both these possibilities are plausible for *Erica*: in the CFR, most species are found in a vegetation type called fynbos which has a highly scattered distribution – from patches on the coast to those spanning the Cape Fold Mountains. One of the remarkable things about fynbos is the way in which the suite of plant species that make up the vegetation changes as you go from place to place; and, as ever, *Erica* is the prime example: there are even individual species found only on single mountain tops. Have those species become isolated and subsequently drifted to become new ones? Might past climatic changes have played a role, causing changes in the distributions of species – moving higher or lower, up and down the mountains with episodes of climatic warming and cooling?

On the other hand there is the immense floral diversity, in particular the apparent differences in pollination mechanism – there are the tiny, dull-coloured

flowers that cast pollen to, and collect pollen from, the wind; a range of general insect-pollinated flower types; those with long, narrow tubes visited specifically by long-tongued flies; the large, brightly coloured, tubular flowers visited by sunbirds (Rebello *et al.* 1985); and even one bizarre species, *E. hanekomii*, that is pollinated by mice (Oliver & Oliver 1999; Turner *et al.* 2011)! How do we set about testing which of these hypotheses are true? Just as in *Jurassic Park*, the key lies in the DNA. The DNA of ancient species is a little more difficult to lay hands on than Michael Crichton might have suggested, so instead we look at the species that are alive today.

The first step is to read the sequence of the DNA code in certain regions of the genome of as many species as possible (Figure 3a & 3b). We then compare these sequences and infer a kind of family tree, otherwise known as a phylogeny, on the basis of shared changes (Figure 3c & 3d). We can then apply a bunch of exciting phylogenetic methodologies to infer, for example, the ages, geographical distributions, and physical characteristics of ancestors (represented in Figure 3d and 3e where the branches of the phylogenetic tree meet). As in any scientific study, our sampling size needs to be large enough to be able to get a statistically significant result. We cannot re-run evolution in order to test our theories (at

Figure 3. A flow-chart for phylogenetic analysis and evolutionary inference methods: a: DNA extraction and Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) amplification of targeted marker regions; b: DNA sequencing; c: alignment of sequences of multiple species; d: phylogenetic analysis; e: molecular dating and ancestral trait reconstruction.

least, not outside the simplified virtual world of a computer), so it is especially important to look at a biological group that exhibits enough of the phenomenon we are interested in. For speciation, *Erica* is the best example in the CFR. So why hasn't anyone tried this before? To understand at first hand the challenges involved, I would thoroughly recommend that you take a walk in the fynbos of the Western Cape and count how many different heathers you can see. If you have a good eye, you might find upwards of 20 species within a few hours of strolling along a path (and a single, well chosen, stride could take you over a handful in one go), by which time you may have no idea whether the one in your hand is new for that day or not. You may need rather longer to put names on them.

As you will probably know, some Cape species are distinctive, but many fall into the notorious "small pink job" category, or are wind-pollinated with tiny flowers and tinier diagnostic characters – if you know what to look for. That, for starters, is why having Ted Oliver on your team is essential. Then you have got to sequence and analyse the DNA. It will be a while before the "next generation" DNA-sequencing technology will be up to dealing with all of the 820-odd species of *Erica*, so this remains a painstaking process. All in all, it is a huge task.

Is it time to give up in disgust and look for an easier project? Of course not! We have done a lot of fieldwork hiking through the fynbos, as well as in heathlands further afield (such as in Madagascar). Numerous friends and colleagues have done the same – for which we are extremely grateful. To date we have managed to lay hands on more than half of all the *Erica* species, which is no mean achievement.

Our first estimate at the phylogeny of *Erica* (Pirie *et al.* 2011) is based only on a single DNA region and is therefore a preliminary result, but from it we can already draw a number of interesting conclusions. Firstly, it is immediately apparent that there were a lot of changes in flower types as the species of *Erica* originated. For example, many of the bird-pollinated species are more closely related to insect-pollinated species than they are to other bird-pollinated ones.

Secondly, there is evidence to suggest that common ancestors of today's *Erica* species dispersed out of Europe onto the African continent. As well as making the giant leap down to the southern tip of Africa, they managed to colonize the mountains of tropical East Africa, and those of Madagascar and a few other islands in the Indian Ocean. In contrast to this impressive record in long-distance dispersal, there are some species-rich groups that did not manage to break out of restricted areas, such as the regions south-west and north-west of the Cape Fold Mountains. The South-West (which includes the Cape Peninsula, Hottentots-Holland and Kogelberg) and North-West (including the Cedarberg, Ceres and Hex River Mountains) regions (see Figure 1) have long been recognized as areas of high endemism (Oliver *et al.* 1983). Our results indicate that many of those unique species originated where they now grow. For

a

b

c

d

Figure 4. *Erica* species of the NW-clade:

a: *E. arachnocalyx*; b: *E. cetrata*; c: *E. lavandulifolia*; d: *E. inflata* (© Petra Wester); e: *E. plumosa*; f: *E. oresigena*; g: *E. senilis* (© Berit Gehrke); h: *E. totta* (© Berit Gehrke); i: *E. rubens*; j: *E. thunbergii* (unless stated otherwise © Ted Oliver).

e

f

g

h

i

j

illustration I have put together a number of (mostly) Ted Oliver's photographs of species of the North-West group (Figures 4 & 5). Clearly the range of flower forms that they represent is immense, including the remarkable *Erica junonia* (Figure 5 left), with long, narrow flowers pollinated by long-proboscid flies; and the mouse-pollinated *E. hanekomii* (Figure 5 right). This pattern of geographically

Figure 5 *Erica* species of the NW-clade: *E. junonia* (left) and *E. hanekomii* (right) (© Ted Oliver).

clustered, but morphologically diverse groups of closely related species seems to be repeated across the CFR. This could point to an answer to my original question: the origin of species of *Erica* might be driven by shifts between different pollinators. This scenario will need to be tested more rigorously when we have more data. There are also more practical applications for phylogenies, such as the classification of species. Various smaller *Erica*-like genera, such as *Phillipia* and *Blaeria*, were once recognized, but recently were re-classified by Ted Oliver (2000) as belonging to *Erica*. This was actually an unusual move – most taxonomists with only morphology to work with have tended to “split” off unusual species into different genera rather than to “lump” them together. Our results, however, clearly support the taxonomic changes: many species of the former “minor” genera are more closely related to different *Erica* species (in the strict sense) than they are to each other. It is more meaningful just to regard them all as *Erica*.

The huge number of species of *Erica* is, however, a bit of a challenge when it comes to remembering species or retrieving information about them, and hence a classification system has been used to divide up the species into more “digestible” groups. Unfortunately, the sections of George Bentham (1839), and Guthrie and Bolus (1905–1907), used to group the Cape species illustrated in Baker and Oliver (1967) and Schumann and Kirsten (1992), fare rather poorly when compared with our new knowledge of relatedness. This is an almost inevitable consequence of all that chopping and changing in flower types that I have mentioned. Floral morphology provided the main defining characteristics of Bentham's, and Guthrie's and Bolus's sections because flowers present many of the distinguishing characters that are most straightforward to observe.

However, when evolution acts to select the same traits in different organisms then those traits just won't reliably diagnose groups. The classification needs revision, but there is a way to go before that should be attempted.

In the meantime, we hope to learn a lot more about *Erica*, and in so doing to learn more about both the CFR and the process of evolution.

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